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ABSTRACTS

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Microbial peroxide-producing cell coupled in-situ enzymatic depolymerization for lignin bio-refinery

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Abstract: Lignin is one of the most versatile and complex macromolecules and can give value-added products like p-coumaric acid and vanillin upon its depolymerization. The current work explored oxidative lignin depolymerization in a microbial peroxide-producing cell containing manganese peroxidase enzymes. A double-chambered microbial peroxide-producing cell was constructed containing the immobilized manganese peroxidase on alginate beads in the cathode chamber, while the anodic chamber contained wastewater. This setup is run for 5-7 days after the addition of lignin in the catholyte. The voltage measured in the circuit was 0.491 V and the current and power densities were 223 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ and 110 $\mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The maximum H_2O_2 concentration observed was 1.5 mM. Depolymerization of lignin was confirmed by the change in the significant peaks at 280 and 314 nm of the UV-Visible spectrum and change in the signature regions of β - β linkages and β -O-4 linkages observed in the FTIR spectrum. LC-QTOF-MS analysis revealed the presence of some compounds primarily including isoeugenol, acetovanillone, methacrylic acid, phenamacril, diofenolan and jasmolin identified as the product of lignin depolymerization.

Keywords: Microbial Peroxide Producing Cell, Manganese Peroxidase, LigninBiorefinery, Fuel Cell, Advanced Oxidation Process.

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